

A DIAMINODINAPHTHYL SULPHIDE

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2:2'-Diacetoxy-6:6'-dinitrodinaphthyl sulphide has been reduced with tin and HCl to yield aminonaphthol.

β -Naphthylamine was treated with sulphur monochloride by Airan and Shah (this *Journal*, 1946, 22, 360), and the compound obtained was assigned the following structure

The original idea was to see if a diaminodinaphthyl sulphide could be obtained, analogous in structure to 2:2'-dihydroxydinaphthyl sulphide, prepared by Henricque (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2993).

The same problem was then tackled indirectly when, as communicated earlier (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 211), 2:2'-diacetoxy-6:6'-dinitrodinaphthyl sulphide was prepared by the present authors.

The present communication deals with the reduction of this nitro derivative. The reduction by tin and hydrochloric acid appears to break the sulphur linkage in addition to reducing the nitro groups. A milder procedure according to the method of Morgan and Micklethwait (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 151), however, reduced the nitro groups retaining the sulphur linkage in tact.

EXPERIMENTAL

2:2'-Dihydroxy-6:6'-diaminodinaphthyl Sulphide.—(I). Powdered 2:2'-diacetoxy-6:6'-dinitrodinaphthyl sulphide (5 g.) was mixed thoroughly with zinc dust (7 g.). To this were added 95% alcohol (50 c.c.) and ammonium chloride (1 g.) dissolved in water (5 c.c.). This mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 3 hours, and the clear red solution was filtered hot. The filtrate on dilution gave a red-brown solid which did not melt.

Cold dilute hydrochloric acid was added to this solid and stirred, when its colour changed to green. The mixture was slightly warmed and filtered. The green solid (2 g.) was repeatedly washed with cold benzene, when a portion remained insoluble, whereas the portion which dissolved in benzene crystallised from it as a yellow compound, m. p. 223-24°; mixed m. p. with 2:2'-dihydroxy-6:6'-dinitrodinaphthyl sulphide showing no depression, thus indicating that only deacetylation had taken place. The portion, insoluble in benzene, was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 193-94°.

It contained both nitrogen and sulphur. It is also soluble in acetone and acetic acid. (Found : S, 9.3. $C_{20}H_{16}O_2N_2S$ requires S, 9.19 per cent).

(II). 2:2'-Dihydroxy-6:6'-dinitrodinaphthyl sulphide (5 g.) was mixed with zinc dust (7 g.) and refluxed on a water-bath for 3 hours with the same amount of alcohol and ammonium chloride as taken previously. The subsequent treatment was also the same as on the previous occasion. This also ultimately yielded a green compound (1.5 g.) insoluble in benzene, and soluble in alcohol, m.p. 193-94°. Its mixed melting point with similar compound obtained as in (1), remained undepressed. When coupled with β -naphthol it gave a product, m. p. 263-65°, containing no sulphur.

After the reduction, also some unreacted 2:2'-dihydroxy 6:6'-dinitrodinaphthyl sulphide could be recovered.

6-Amino-2-Naphthol.—(A). To 2:2'-diacetoxy-6:6'-dinitrodinaphthyl sulphide (5 g.) were added granulated tin (20 g.) and pure concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.) and the reaction mixture refluxed on a wire gauze. Within half an hour an orange solution was formed. More hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.) was added and refluxing continued for 3½ hours. The reaction mixture was filtered hot through cotton wool, and allowed to cool. The solution became turbid on cooling. It was then diluted and the tin completely removed by passing hydrogen sulphide. The yellow colour of the filtrate changed to red on the addition of ammonia, and a violet coloured solid separated out. It contained nitrogen, but no sulphur, m.p. 190-95° (*Ber.*, 1906, 39 3006).

(B). 2:2'-Dihydroxy-6:6'-dinitrodinaphthyl sulphide was also similarly reduced with tin and hydrochloric acid. The hydrochloride of the reduction product was crystallised from water, m.p. 229-230°.

This latter compound on treatment with dilute ammonia gave a violet compound, containing no sulphur, m.p. 192-194°. It was identical with the violet compound obtained in (A) above.

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